

SHORT COMMUNICATIONS.

Revised Structure of Erianthin—A Flavonol from *Blumea eriantha* DC

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Isolation of a new flavonol, erianthin, from *Blumea eriantha* DC was reported by Bose and Dutt in 1940 and they suggested its structure as 5 : 7-dihydroxy-3 : 3' : 4' : 6 : 8-pentamethoxy flavone¹ which was however not substantiated by synthesis². In view of the above discrepancy, the problem has been re-investigated by us and the results are presented below.

Previously assigned molecular formula of erianthin $C_{20}H_{20}O_9$, m.p. 161°, has now been revised to $C_{20}H_{20}O_8$ (M^+ 388) and the diacetate ($C_{24}H_{24}O_{11}$, m.p. 163°) described earlier (*loc. cit.*) has now been found to be a monoacetate $C_{22}H_{22}O_9$ (M^+ 430), on the basis of mass spectral analysis. Erianthin, on treatment with diazomethane, was reported to furnish a monomethyl ether ($C_{21}H_{22}O_9$, m.p. 141°) which gave positive ferric chloride coloration and formed an acetate. The above monomethyl ether has now been found by t. l. c. to be a mixture of erianthin and its monomethyl ether (Ic), $C_{21}H_{22}O_8$, m.p. 157-58°, which explains the positive ferric reaction and the formation of an acetate now identified as erianthin monoacetate (Ib).

Erianthin gave positive ferric chloride coloration but its I. R. spectrum did not show any band for free hydroxyl group, thus suggesting the presence of the chelated 5-hydroxyl group. On refluxing with ethanolic caustic potash, erianthin furnished veratric acid which indicated the presence of two methoxyl groups at 3' and 4' positions (*loc. cit.*). The U. V. spectrum of erianthin $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{EtOH}}$ 348 $m\mu$ (Band I), 273 and 256 $m\mu$ (Band II) ; ($\log \epsilon$ 4.48, 4.34 and 4.39 respectively) also corroborated the above conclusion as Band II showed two peaks at 273 and 256 $m\mu$ which is characteristic

- a, R = H
 b, R = COCH₃
 c, R = CH₃

1. P. K. Bose and P. Dutt, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 17, 45.
2. T. R. Seshadri and V. Venkateswarlu, *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1946, 23A, 192.

of flavones and flavonols having methoxyl or hydroxyl groups at 3' and 4' positions^{3a}. The mass spectrum of erianthin showed the molecular ion at m/e 388 (base peak) together with an intense (85 percent of the base peak) peak at m/e 373 (M-15; M-CH₃) arising by the facile loss of Me from the 6-methoxyl group⁴.

The U. V. spectrum of erianthin is very similar to that of 5-hydroxy-3 : 3' : 4' : 6 : 7-pentamethoxy flavone, Ia, (= quercetagenin pentamethyl ether)^{3b, 5, 6}. Moreover, the melting points of erianthin, its monoacetate and monomethyl ether are same as those of quercetagenin pentamethyl ether and its corresponding derivatives. Thus there is hardly any doubt that erianthin is 5-hydroxy-3 : 3' : 4' : 6 : 7-pentamethoxy flavone (Ia). It should be mentioned here that quercetagenin pentamethyl ether has recently been isolated from two other plants *Artemisia absinthium*⁵ and *Kuhnia eupatorioides*⁶.

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- 3b. *ibid.*, p. 427.
4. D. L. Dreyer and D. J. Bertelli, *Tetrahedron*, 1967, **23**, 4607.
5. Z. Cekan and V. Herout, *Chem. Listy*, 1955, **49**, 1053.
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